

TREATMENT OF ACUTE SINUSITIS IN CHILDREN WITH LOCAL ANTIBACTERIAL DRUGS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11047085>

Symptoms of sinusitis significantly reduce the quality of life of patients. Complaints such as difficulty in nasal breathing, nasal discharge, headaches appear, the sense of smell changes, sleep is disturbed, and the ability to work decreases. In the acute stage of sinusitis, when a virus enters, swelling quickly forms in the maxillary sinuses, the production of mucous gland secretions increases and the epithelium sloughs off. The natural anastomosis is blocked, the drainage function, ventilation of the maxillary sinuses, gas exchange and natural aeration in the nasal sinuses are disrupted, which leads to the accumulation of exudate. All this favors the activation of saprophytic flora in the sinus and the viral inflammation already turns into bacterial. A vicious circle is created in which swelling of the mucous membrane leads to disruption of mucociliary transport and accumulation of stagnant secretions in the maxillary sinuses, and the growth of bacteria aggravates inflammation, which finally blocks the anastomosis. Infection from the maxillary sinuses can spread to neighboring areas and cause other pathologies.

Despite modern diagnostic and treatment methods, there is no tendency to reduce the pathology of the paranasal sinuses. Based on statistics, acute sinusitis is widespread among all age groups, but the largest number of patients is between the ages of 4 and 15 years. Among all diseases of the upper respiratory tract in recent years, the incidence of diseases of the nose and paranasal sinuses in children was 35-37%. The likelihood of developing sinusitis increases during the cold season, for example, during the autumn-winter period.

Acute sinusitis is dangerous due to various pathological complications. Timely and effective treatment is a prerequisite for recovery. Oral or parenteral administration of antibacterial drugs, in addition to the positive effect, creates conditions for the development of dysbiosis due to the inhibition of intestinal microflora, promotes colonization by strains of nosocomial infection on the mucous membranes, especially in closed cavities, such as the maxillary sinuses. An alternative is a local effect on the paranasal sinuses. Unlike the systemic use of antibiotics, local use has a number of advantages: it eliminates the negative systemic effect of antibacterial therapy, requires a smaller therapeutic dose of

the drug, which is administered directly to the site of inflammation, which contributes to a longer preservation of the antibacterial drug in the sinus cavity. It has been experimentally proven that when a therapeutic dose of the drug is administered, 50% of the minimum inhibitory concentration of the antibacterial drug remains in the sinus for 12 hours.

The purpose of this study:

Assessing the effectiveness of the use of local antibacterial drugs, as well as the advisability of using topical mucolytic drugs for acute sinusitis.

Mandatory conditions are the activity of the antibiotic against the pathogen, a sufficient concentration of the antibiotic at the site of infection and maintaining this concentration for the required time.

Thanks to the maximum information content and atraumatic nature of the endoscopic examination, it is possible to see areas of the nasal cavity that are inaccessible during rhinoscopy. Modern endoscopes help to conduct a thorough examination of the cavity, anastomosis, and structures of the nasopharynx; also, using an endoscope for biopsy, they take part of the mucus directly from the site of inflammation.

The study was conducted in the autumn-winter period on 40 patients aged 12 to 15 years with a history of acute maxillary sinusitis at the time of the study. The inhaled antibiotic framycetin (active substance framycetin sulfate), intended for the treatment of acute infectious diseases of the upper respiratory tract, was used as a local antibacterial drug.

The results of this study showed that by the 7th day of treatment, the function of the ciliated epithelium was restored. Maximum effectiveness was achieved only in those cases in which the sinus anastomosis is well passable, which indicates the advisability of the combined use of topical mucolytic and antibacterial drugs.

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